

CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant:

By signing and submitting this proposal, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding debarment and suspension, drug-free workplace, and lobbying activities (see below), nondiscrimination, and flood hazard insurance (when applicable) as set forth in the NSF Proposal & Award Policies & Procedures Guide, Part I: the Grant Proposal Guide (GPG) (NSF 08-1). Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuing award is a criminal offense (U. S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

Conflict of Interest Certification

In addition, if the applicant institution employs more than fifty persons, by electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative of the applicant institution is certifying that the institution has implemented a written and enforced conflict of interest policy that is consistent with the provisions of the NSF Proposal & Award Policies & Procedures Guide, Part II, Award & Administration Guide (AAG) Chapter IV.A; that to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by that conflict of interest policy have been made; and that all identified conflicts of interest will have been satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated prior to the institution's expenditure of any funds under the award, in accordance with the institution's conflict of interest policy. Conflicts which cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated must be disclosed to NSF.

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(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Debarment and Suspension Certification contained in Exhibit II-4 of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Lobbying

The following certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

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- (1) No federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.
- (2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure of Lobbying Activities," in accordance with its instructions.
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- (2) building (and any related equipment) is covered by adequate flood insurance.

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- (1) for NSF grants for the construction of a building or facility, regardless of the dollar amount of the grant; and
- (2) for other NSF Grants when more than \$25,000 has been budgeted in the proposal for repair, alteration or improvement (construction) of a building or facility.

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PROJECT SUMMARY

NESCent, the National Evolutionary Synthesis Center, was first funded in 2004 to “serve the needs of the evolutionary biology community by providing mechanisms to foster synthetic, collaborative, cross-disciplinary studies” as a collaborative venture of Duke University, the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill and North Carolina State University. In its first 4 years NESCent has brought over 2300 scientists to the Center, and has funded over 120 group meetings, 21 postdocs and 38 sabbatical and other visiting scholars largely through a community driven proposal process. It has established a vibrant in-house community of scientists and informatics specialists, and has supported activities leading to over 100 publications covering virtually all aspects of evolutionary biology. NESCent has taken the lead in developing evoinformatics. It has provided the leadership in establishing a major collaboration with evolutionary biology journals and societies to develop Dryad, a digital data repository for evolutionary biology. NESCent has sponsored hackathons to expand the interoperability of open source software tools for evolutionary biology, and offered a number of training opportunities in evoinformatics. NESCent has established a wide variety of partnerships with major groups in evolutionary biology and education. The Center offers a number of programs targeted towards increasing participation of underserved groups, and has leveraged its impact by developing partnerships with over 100 different organizations.

In the next five years NESCent proposes to extend its contributions by continuing the most successful current programs and adding a number of new programs that include:

- Introducing targeted initiatives that will jumpstart new areas of evolutionary synthesis, including areas important to human affairs such as climate change, health and disease, and areas of broad interdisciplinary scope such as cultural evolution.
- Encouraging major initiatives that combine individual programs such as sabbaticals, postdocs and working groups around integrated topics to reap the benefits of synergistic activity.
- Funding an expanded role for graduate students in its synthetic science programs.
- With the community, identifying new areas for major cyberinfrastructure initiatives in evolutionary biology such as visualization.
- Developing new programs to more aggressively recruit those from underserved groups to participate in evolutionary biology, and to more effectively and broadly communicate the science produced at the Center to the education community and general public.
- Collaborating with social scientists studying the nature of scientific collaborations and networks to establish a rigorous approach to assess the Center’s work and understand its impact in scientific progress and role in culture change.

Intellectual merit

The intellectual merit of the Center rests in the strength of the peer-reviewed sponsored science program, which has a demonstrated ability to produce innovative, high-impact, synthetic research products. It has taken the lead in developing cyberinfrastructure that promotes the integration of tools and data within evolutionary biology and across biological disciplines. As a Center NESCent can uniquely work to build collaborative research communities, foster a culture of data sharing, and partner with organizations all over the world.

Broader impacts

All of NESCent’s activities are directed towards supporting the broader evolutionary biology community in its pursuit of synthetic evolutionary biology. NESCent promotes changes in the culture of collaboration and data sharing, and facilitates the development, building and consensus of scientific communities that are essential for truly transformative research. NESCent provides critical infrastructure – in terms of funding, logistics, physical space, and informatics to allow new synthetic breakthroughs. It provides new cyberinfrastructure resources to the entire evolutionary biology community. It offers a wide variety of training and outreach activities aimed at the general public, the citizen scientist, the student, the educator and the practicing evolutionary biologist. It devotes significant effort into recruiting individuals from groups under represented in evolutionary biology into all activities – science, informatics and education.

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I INTRODUCTION – A VISION FOR THE CENTER

Evolutionary biology is fundamentally a synthetic science. From Darwin's first exposition 150 years ago in the *Origin of Species*, to the "Modern Synthesis" that established the contemporary field of evolutionary biology in the middle of the 20th century, the most important contributions have been those that integrate data, concepts and approaches from a wide range of fields to produce a new and different whole. Evolutionary biology has always existed at the intersection of many disparate bodies of data and theory: patterns through time and in the present; the relation of the genotype and the phenotype; hierarchical relations in the individual, the population and the ecosystem; and the diversity emerging from the tree of life. A [workshop](#) sponsored by the National Science Foundation in 2001-02 eloquently laid out the vision for an Evolutionary Synthesis Center, and convincingly detailed the components and value of such a center.

In 2003 NSF sent out a [RFP](#) for a center that would "serve the needs of the evolutionary biology community by providing mechanisms to foster synthetic, collaborative, cross-disciplinary studies. It will play a pivotal role in the further unification of the biological sciences as it draws together knowledge from disparate biological fields to increase our general understanding of biological design and function." In response to that call, a consortium of three universities in North Carolina (Duke University [Duke], University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill [UNC] and North Carolina State University [NCSU]) proposed to establish such a center in collaboration, leveraging the rich resources in genetics, evolutionary biology and informatics at the three universities. Funding for NESCent was awarded in 2004, and the Center was established in December of 2004.

During the first four years of existence, the Center has worked to achieve the goals set forth in the RFP and our initial proposal. Our over-riding goal has been to facilitate synthetic research in evolutionary biology as proposed by the evolutionary biology community. Through our proposal process we have funded hundreds of scientists representing the full spectrum of evolutionary biology. Some of this funding has been used to catalyze groups of individuals that have never before met in the same room, bringing diverse methods, theories and data to bear on a common issue. Other funding has provided both junior and senior scientists the time and environment to explore their ideas fully leading to new insight and understanding. For some, it has involved developing and providing just the right informatic or analytical tool that makes scientific advances not previously possible achievable. This function – the facilitation of cutting edge, synthetic, interdisciplinary evolutionary biology as brought to us by the community – is a core function and commitment that is, and will remain, central to our operations. During working groups, catalysis meetings, hackathons and summer courses the atmosphere of excitement is palpable: "great networking, very fast rate of productivity, meeting of minds that is hard to accomplish when people are distributed worldwide" (comment from a participant).

As we have matured, we have ourselves defined and developed major initiatives that provide the underpinning to actively move the community forward. While we have many avenues for community input, such as our September 2008 [community summit](#), NESCent has assumed a proactive leadership role, particularly in the field of evolutionary informatics. A hallmark of NESCent is the close association of our informatics and science programs. Many of our informatics initiatives, such as Dryad, Phenoscape, and our hackathon program, are prime examples of the synergy that emerges when the right combination of informatics expertise and scientific goals are brought together; arguably this association can only happen in the collaborative context provided by a center such as NESCent.

In parallel with our science and informatics programs, we have developed activities that increase the public understanding of evolutionary biology and put effective teaching resources in the hands of educators. We have established programs to promote demographic diversity within our own activities and in the field of evolutionary biology more generally.

Our vision of a Synthesis Center is to provide an environment for transformational science that cannot be achieved on the scale of individual investigator projects. The value added by a center such as NESCent lies on four foundations. First, NESCent's science is community driven and a core activity of the Center is

community building. While Darwin may have single-handedly synthesized of the available knowledge of his time, today's synthesis is best achieved by cross-disciplinary, multi-talented groups that bring diverse perspectives and expertise to the table. Second, we actively work to build a culture of collaboration and data sharing. This has culminated in a discipline-wide initiative to make the data underlying published works available. Third, the close association of our science, informatics and educational programs allows extraordinary synergies to develop. Finally, the Center acts as a focal point for a wide network of partnerships and associations, nationally and internationally, that allows us to leverage our impact. As we go forward, we will consolidate the best of the past four years while putting forth new programs that build upon the above strengths of the Center. Our themes in looking forward are threefold: greater **focus** to our activities; an emphasis on further developing **synergy** among our efforts and across fields; and increased **outreach and training**.

II RESULTS FROM PRIOR SUPPORT

A. Overview

The activities of a center such as NESCent are difficult to summarize in a brief format and hence in this proposal we can only sketch a few examples. In the first 4 years of its existence, over 2300 scientists have visited the Center participating in over 120 meetings of various types. We have supported 21 postdoctoral fellows, 38 sabbatical scholars and visiting scientists, 24 working groups and 14 catalysis meetings. These projects span the full spectrum of evolutionary topics and perspectives from genome and molecular evolution to biodiversity and the history of life. NESCent has pioneered creative new initiatives in evolutionary biology such as hackathons to promote the collaborative development of open source software tools in evoinformatics. We have offered popular new summer courses in the use of advanced informatics tools for evolutionary biology. NESCent has developed a wide range of activities in education and outreach, to bring evolutionary biology to the community and encourage participation of members of underserved groups in evolutionary biology. We have had visitors from every state in the US but 4, and participants from 32 countries. Our funding has contributed to more than 175 new publications, successful grant proposals, software tools, and other products during the past 3 years (Table 1). The sabbatical and working group projects have been particularly productive, and the number of publications resulting from postdoctoral and working group projects has more than doubled in the past 9 months. Details of these activities and products may be found on our website, in our annual reviews, as well as in the supplemental data on our [public documents page](#).

Table 1. Products from NESCent science projects, cumulative through September 2008. Numbers in parentheses indicate submitted papers or proposals. Our research indicates that these products are under-reported by at least 25%.						
Products:	Postdoc	Sabbaticals	Working Groups	Catalysis Meetings	Other	Totals
Publications	22 (12)	51 (4)	41 (22)	3 (2)	8 (4)	125 (44)
Grants	3 (2)	5	4 (3)	4 (7)	3 (4)	19 (16)
Software	13	1	9 (1)	1	9	33 (1)

B. NESCent Activities in Years 1 through 4 – Some Examples

Synthesis is a process that combines two or more pre-existing elements resulting in the formation of something new. Synthetic science involves combining different pre-existing elements – different scientific communities and perspectives, different data types, different theoretical models and conceptual frameworks or different informatics tools – to create a new and richer level of scientific generality and understanding (Kidd et al., in prep; Hackett et al., 2008). Synthetic research can add enormous value to the primary data accumulated by scientists in diverse fields in recent decades. Here we will provide a few brief examples of supported scientific activities that illustrate NESCent's unique role as we work towards transforming our understanding of important evolutionary challenges.

Major research challenges often require the integration of data, tools and perspectives from multiple research communities that typically do not interact. NESCent catalysis meetings have provided a novel, effective mechanism for bringing together diverse research communities. For example, a catalysis meeting on “Evolution in Contemporary Human Populations”, organized by Stephen Stearns, Peter Byers and Diddahally Govindaraju, brought together physicians, geneticists, epidemiologists, ethicists, anthropologists and evolutionary biologists. One major theme focused on how evolutionary questions of medical significance can be addressed by integrating data from epidemiological studies with emerging data from the human genome, HapMap and related projects. The catalysis meeting led to a series of new research collaborations, including a successful NESCent working group (organized by Govindaraju, Stearns, Andy Clark, and Trudy Mackay) that is combining SNP and other genetic data to analyze evolutionary patterns in data generated from the three-generation US Framingham Heart Study. This group has further built momentum by organizing an [Arthur M. Sackler colloquium](#) at the National Academy of Sciences. Our Education and Outreach group used this meeting as a springboard to organize material for a symposium on [Evolution and Medicine](#) at the National Association of Biology Teachers, and prepared an article on this meeting for educators ([Hood and Jenkins 2008](#)).

Another catalysis meeting, organized by Anne Yoder and Claire Kremen, examined how evolutionary history can inform conservation planning in Madagascar. The meeting brought together systematics for many taxa, paleontology and geology, geography, theoretical phylogenetics and niche modeling and conservation biology to explore patterns of biodiversity in Madagascar. The meeting generated a major *Science* article (Kremen et al. 2008) on aligning conservation priorities across taxa, a MacArthur Foundation proposal on identifying evolutionary hotspots, and several additional articles as well as a review, commissioned by NESCent in [actionbioscience.org](#) for the public. Importantly a large number of new collaborations were born at this meeting including a group examining the question of developing environmental layers for deep-time slices; a group exploring ways to bridge present-day niche modeling with allele distributions using coalescent models and methods; a group examining colonization times across a broad array of animals, plants and fungi at deep phylogenetic levels to understand the history of community assemblages; and a group that will explore the effects of geological substrate and climate on patterns of biodiversity distribution, with a focus on areas of high local endemism.

These are just 2 of the 14 catalysis meetings we have funded thus far; these meetings have been very effective in generating new interdisciplinary collaborations and identifying exciting new directions for synthetic evolutionary research.

A common theme of many NESCent working groups and other projects is integrating different types of data to address broad evolutionary questions. One of our first working groups, organized by Paula Mabee and Monte Westerfield, explored morphological evolution in fish by combining two rich data resources: developmental mutants that alter morphological phenotypes in the zebrafish model system; and natural phenotypic diversity in the Cypriniform clade of fishes. The work of this group provided clear evidence that such an approach would be of deep value for understanding evolutionary diversification far beyond the bounds of this specific question or this group of organisms. This working group laid the foundation for Mabee and Westerfield, and NESCent’s Informatics group (led by Vision) obtained a major NSF grant (BDI-0641025) for a project, named [Phenoscape](#), that involves a collaboration among the zebrafish database group (ZFIN), the Cypriniform Tree of Life project, the DeepFin RCN, and the National Center for Biomedical Ontologies (NCBO). The project is developing new ontologies and software tools to study the evolution of phenotype through the integration of existing developmental genetic and phylogenetic knowledge (Mabee et al., 2007). NESCent is disseminating this work through publications and software tools, and workshops on ontologies for evolutionary biology, including one held at the 2008 Evolution meetings, and two upcoming workshops at the 2009 meetings of the Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology and the American Society of Ichthyologists and Herpetologists.

Other NESCent working groups have focused on data assembly and analysis (e.g., “The Paradox of Mixed Mating Systems in Plants”; “Evolution and Development of Polyphenisms”); on development of new theoretical approaches (e.g., “Mathematical Models, Microbes and Evolutionary Diversification”) and on assembly of important informatics tools (e.g., “Synthesizing Computational Resources for cis-regulatory Evolution”).

Synthetic research requires the availability of data from investigations and of software tools for analysis. A core priority for NESCent is to promote a culture of widespread data-sharing and open source software development for evolutionary analysis. Because there are only a handful of specialized repositories for evolutionary biology data (such as TreeBASE, discussed below), the data underlying most published work in evolutionary biology is not readily available for examination or re-use by others. NESCent has taken the lead in establishing a general-purpose digital data repository for evolutionary biology, ecology and related disciplines, [Dryad](#), in collaboration with a consortium of scientific societies and journals. Not only has NESCent provided the technical underpinnings for such a repository, but NESCent staff members, in collaboration with NESCent sabbatical scholar, Michael Whitlock, have provided leadership in working with major societies and journals to develop a joint data sharing policy. Currently several different societies are moving towards requiring data submission as a precondition to publication. Dryad will provide the infrastructure needed to realize this goal by simplifying the process by which authors can submit any kind of data, providing persistent, resolvable and globally unique identifiers for datasets, and allowing sophisticated search and retrieval for datasets from many different journals. NESCent has recently received a NSF BDI (DBI-0743720) grant to develop the data repository and assemble a Management Board of representatives from journals and societies to oversee management, development of repository policies (e.g. governing intellectual property), and financial sustainability.

NESCent plays an analogous role in community development of open-source software for evolutionary synthesis. Evolutionary biologists have collectively developed and use a plethora of specialty software programs to perform a wide variety of analyses. Unfortunately, these programs are largely platform-specific, require idiosyncratic and conflicting file formats, and lack effective user support, maintenance, and graphic interfaces. NESCent has promoted community-wide collaborative development of open source software tools for evolutionary biology. One of NESCent's most original and important contributions in this regard is the [hackathon](#) (Lapp et al., 2007), a working meeting focused on user-driven informatics goals in which participants collaboratively write code for shared open-source software libraries (e.g. BioPerl, R). One recent hackathon, focusing on Comparative Phylogenetic Methods in R, was proposed and organized by three NESCent postdocs (Samantha Price, Amy Zanne, and Brian O'Meara). The resources produced by this intensely productive meeting, have already had significant impact on researchers using phylogenetic methods. Since January, 2008 there have been over 2992 unique visitors to the [r-phylo.org wiki](#), 168 communications on the R-phylo special interest group mailing list, and consensus on a community standard for phylogenetic data representation in R supported by a new package named phylobase (O'Meara et al., 2008).

The combination of NESCent's in-house community of researchers and the visiting meeting participants provides unique opportunities for new collaborative synthesis. In particular, NESCent postdocs have been involved in a variety of working group projects. As one example, Amy Zanne's postdoctoral project (2006-2008) explored the evolution of functional traits involved in water and nutrient transport and mechanical support in plants. She collaborated with multiple working groups at NESCent, NCEAS, the Australian Research Council (ARC), and International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP), and organized a joint NESCent-ARC working group, to develop a series of interrelated databases for vegetation and plant functional and anatomical traits. These collaborations have generated a set of new database resources for understanding the connections among environmental change and the evolution of plant function and they have resulted in multiple publications.

One of the value-added components of the in house community of postdoctoral fellows, sabbatical scholars and other resident scientists is the possibility for serendipitous collaborations. The recent collaboration between postdoctoral fellow Derrick Zwickl and sabbatical scholar Paul Lewis provides an example. At NESCent Lewis and Zwickl began discussions about modeling rate variation within phylogenetic analyses. These discussions allowed them to understand the limitations of current approaches and to develop a more general and flexible approach, termed FLEX. Lewis and Zwickl each implemented a form of FLEX in their software programs (Phycas and GARLI, respectively). This opportunistic collaboration resulting from their simultaneous projects at NESCent has generated new, open-source software tools that are being widely adopted (e.g. 800 downloads of GARLI version 0.96 since May 2008 release).

The NESCent postdoctoral program aims to train a new generation of scientists well versed in the perspectives and approaches of synthetic science. Rather than working for an individual PI, NESCent postdoctoral fellows are encouraged to establish a range of mentoring and collaborative relationships (see postdoc information on our [documents page](#)). Each postdoc develops his or her own synthetic research program, and often works closely with informatics staff or local senior scientists. At the same time, NESCent provides an explicit postdoc professional training series with a wide variety of career development activities including workshops on teaching, open discussions on professional matters such as publishing, grant writing, ethics, etc., and one-on-one training in teaching and seminar preparation. Thus far, 10 postdocs have left NESCent -- 5 to tenure track positions and another 5 to another postdoctoral position.

NESCent has formed active education and outreach partnerships with multiple national organizations and research teams that are focused on improving science education and the public understanding of science. For example, together with AIBS, NESCent has organized a symposium on Evolution at the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT) annual conference. In addition to symposium organization, NESCent staff have provided associated instructional material both on line and in the form of a [CD](#). NESCent has also disseminated evolutionary biology to the broader educational community through production of “Evolution in the News” web content and podcasts, in collaboration with UC Berkeley’s Museum of Paleontology’s “Understanding Evolution” web project. These projects meet our goal of providing material on cutting edge evolutionary biology in a way that is accessible to teachers and the public. NESCent science and outreach activities are linked in other ways as well. Through working groups and other events, NESCent is involved in national educational initiatives such as the “Evolution Across the Curriculum” concept and the NSF funded Evolutionary Studies (EvoS) expansion, as well as coordinating efforts with other major initiatives such as NCEAS, iPlant and the Encyclopedia of Life.

NESCent has developed a broad range of activities to recruit members of underrepresented groups into its activities; these efforts span all branches of Center programs. We offer targeted sabbatical positions to recruit faculty from historically minority serving institutions and we have worked with faculty from these institutions to develop useful strategies towards minority recruitment through our Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU) working group. We actively recruit scientists from underrepresented groups into our science programs and encourage NESCent-funded PIs to include such scientists in their meetings. We offer scholarships to students from underrepresented groups to attend our informatics courses and have worked with individuals from the SSE and SSB (Scott Edwards and Rich Kliman) to support and coordinate a program to bring promising undergraduates to national meetings. We have taken the lead in developing highly lauded and popular programs on careers in evolution and ecology at the Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS) meeting. Further details on programs and activities may be found in our annual reports.

Finally NESCent has leveraged its reach by partnering with hundreds of groups in science, education, informatics, and the public understanding of science.

C. The Value of a Synthesis Center

We believe a synthesis center provides the physical, virtual and intellectual environment for transformational science that cannot be achieved on the scale of individual investigator or even traditional collaborative projects. In this sense, NESCent provides the scientific integration network for synthetic research in evolutionary biology. NESCent’s unique contribution arises out of four foundational elements:

First, the heart of NESCent’s contribution is **community building**. All our activities – from our vibrant in-house community of postdocs, local and sabbatical scholars, and informatics staff, to our innovative catalysis meetings and hackathons – bring different communities together to address common problems. Evolutionary biology is broad, diverse and complex, and true breakthroughs will come when distinct perspectives, expertise and interests are combined towards a new and synthetic whole.

A second foundation of our work is our commitment to promote **a culture of collaboration**, data sharing and open software development. One of the greatest barriers to synthetic breakthrough is the lack of

access to data or appropriate tools. Increasing access to data and tools pervades all our activities and is the central component of Dryad, our data sharing initiative. NESCent's role in leading and driving this effort forward may transform the way evolutionary biologists regard their data well into the future.

A third foundation of our ability to add value arises from the **synergies** that exist at a physical center such as NESCent. Foremost among these is the close collaboration between our outstanding in house informatics staff and the scientists whose work we support. Few individual investigators can call on this kind of expertise. Similarly our cyberinfrastructure initiatives have all been developed hand in hand with our community of scientists and our outreach and educational initiatives exist in close association with our science and informatics programs. NESCent's "branches" function as an integrated and synergistic whole.

A final contribution, possible only with a center such as NESCent arises from the fact that we are a **Center**, a neutral broker that exists only to promote the most promising, potentially transformational work. Although we have, and will increasingly take a guiding role for some activities, we are not identified with any field, approach, side or position. We may therefore bring groups with divergent views closer together; we may nudge individuals towards common data standards or software interoperability; we may partner with many different kinds of organizations to leverage our impact. NESCent represents the perspective, and provides the expertise, of the evolutionary biology community, within the larger network of organizations always working towards greater scientific communication, collaboration, impact and understanding.

III NESCENT IN YEARS 6-10

In years 6-10, NESCent will continue its core missions of enabling synthetic research, developing and disseminating new tools for evolutionary informatics, and increasing the public understanding of science. We have three major goals as we build on the accomplishments of the first four years. We will develop increased **focus** for our activities, as we take a larger leadership role in driving the activities forward; we will take advantage of the power of increased **synergy**, within and between our major activities; and we will increase our **training** role, so to translate the scientific advances arising from NESCent to both the broader scientific community and the public.

A. Enabling Synthetic Research in Evolutionary Biology

NESCent's science programs in the first five years have emphasized the central element of NSF's original RFP: to create a center for synthetic research in evolutionary biology that engages and supports the national and international communities of researchers interested in diverse aspects of evolution. The cornerstone of our scientific efforts has been an open proposal and review system that fosters the ideas and energies of these research communities. Our scientific mission has intentionally been "all over the map", in terms of geography, research communities, and biological disciplines. As illustrated above, this approach has enabled us to successfully establish a diverse, interdisciplinary portfolio of research projects, primarily involving postdoctoral and faculty researchers. (See our [public documents](#) page for details.)

In the next five years we will continue our open system for proposals in all areas of evolutionary biology, but will incorporate three new themes into our science programs. We will **focus** our efforts on a number of selected research topics that have great potential for advances in synthetic research, by targeting and sustaining activities in those areas. We will encourage **synergy** by supporting greater coordination among different activities and projects – including working groups, postdocs, sabbatical scholars, and graduate students – that have common research themes. We will incorporate graduate student **training** as a major new element of our synthetic research programs. These themes will be addressed both by extending our current programs and by introducing several major new initiatives into our science programs.

1. Extending Current Programs

Our open-proposal system of sponsored science projects has been very successful in generating productive synthetic research in diverse areas relevant to evolution. This has been essential to engaging the national and international communities of evolution researchers with NESCent. We propose to continue these programs for our main science activities – catalysis meetings, working groups, sabbatical scholars, postdoctoral fellows and short-term visitors – through open calls for proposals in all areas of evolutionary biology. In addition, we will continue our targeted sabbatical scholar program for faculty from minority serving institutions for projects that enhance research, education and outreach activities at these institutions. As before, proposals will be reviewed by members of our Advisory Board. We will continue to review and support proposals and projects that combine ecology and evolution jointly with NCEAS, and will explore the possibility of supporting projects jointly with the new National Institute for Mathematical and Biological Synthesis (NIMBioS) and BioSynC (EOL) as appropriate.

We will extend these programs in several important ways, to increase their educational and scientific impact and productivity.

Increased coordination: We will promote increased coordination among proposals and projects involving different project types, especially working groups, postdocs and sabbatical scholars. We will encourage linked collaborative proposals (e.g., between a working group and a postdoc or sabbatical scholar). Our goal is to create greater synergies between our in-house and meeting activities to enhance the productivity of our science programs.

Graduate student involvement: We will greatly expand involvement by graduate students in scientific activities at NESCent. We will require graduate student participation in all catalysis meetings, and strongly encourage such participation in working groups; graduate student involvement will be a criterion for evaluation of NESCent proposals. Several other new initiatives in science and training will also increase graduate student involvement at NESCent (see below).

Support for working groups: We will increase the standard number of meetings for each working group from 3 to 4, to ensure greater opportunities for product completion and follow-up. We will also increase the supplemental funding in support of each working group to provide greater flexibility in meeting project needs (e.g. support for data entry, planning meetings, programming, graduate student support, etc).

2. New Science Initiatives

While we will continue to solicit community based proposals for synthetic projects, NESCent will take an active role in promoting catalysis and synthesis in targeted research areas that have great potential for important advances in evolutionary biology. The NESCent community summit in September 2008 provided strong support for the idea that focusing on selected research areas could further increase NESCent's scientific impacts. There are two main elements to these efforts, targeting catalysis, and targeting synthesis.

Targeting catalysis: Promoting promising partnerships. Our catalysis meetings have been highly successful in bringing together different communities of scientists with a common interest in evolutionary questions. These meetings have generated new research collaborations and new synthetic research in a variety of ways. It is clear there are many further opportunities for promising partnerships between fields that involve topics where an open call for proposals may not be sufficient. This is particularly true for research questions or approaches to evolution that extend beyond academic biology, including social sciences and applied aspects of evolution. One example that emerged from the 2008 NESCent community summit involved the evolution of human languages. This issue is a fundamental and long-standing challenge with a long scholarly tradition in historical and comparative linguistics. Recent applications of phylogenetic methods to linguistic data have provided tantalizing hypotheses about the relationships among different language groups. But there is widespread disagreement (and likely misunderstanding) between phylogeneticists and linguists on the validity and interpretation of these

analyses, and it is unclear whether phylogenetic (tree-based) approaches are the most appropriate analytic framework for describing linguistic evolution. A catalysis meeting bringing together linguists, phylogeneticists, population geneticists, and other evolutionary and social scientists would generate new collaborations and establish fruitful new directions for modeling language evolution; it could also provide a model for future activities combining evolutionary biology and social sciences.

We propose to initiate and support three Center generated catalysis meetings during the first two years of funding that address questions that are particularly ripe for synthesis or that span broadly divergent fields. We will, in effect, catalyze catalysis. The topics for these targeted meetings will be selected in consultation with our Advisory Board, starting at their fall 2009 board meeting. NESCent directors will identify and work with key individuals to identify the needed disciplinary perspectives and participants and to set the agenda for each meeting. Our goal is for these meetings to produce new collaborations and lead to new synthetic research at NESCent and in other venues.

Targeting Synthesis: Targeted calls for proposals. Many major synthetic research challenges are greater than the scope of a single project such as a working group or postdoc. A coordinated set of activities that focus on a single topic will effectively allow sustained progress. Potential topics for major efforts that emerged from the NESCent community summit include visualization of complex evolutionary data (discussed in more detail below); using prospective evolutionary models for developing strategies addressing disease, disease resistance and resource management; metagenomics and microbial diversity; and evolutionary responses to climate change.

We propose two targeted calls for proposals on a specific research theme, with one theme in year 6 and a second in year 8. The topics for these themes will be selected in consultation with our Advisory Board, with the first theme identified at the winter 2010 board meeting. Themes will be chosen based on both scientific importance and broader societal and cultural impacts. The evaluation and selection process will be in two stages: a brief pre-proposal outlining the proposed activities and likely outcomes, and then a longer proposal describing the projects, activities, participants, and products. We will strongly encourage coordination among different project types (e.g., among working groups, postdocs, sabbatical scholars and graduate fellows) in joint proposals and will work with PI's to fully develop the full proposal. We will also consider proposals for distributed graduate seminars as part of our targeted CFPs. We propose to support up to 6 related projects within each research theme, with projects running over a two-year period, and have designated additional funds for these projects.

3. Graduate Student Fellowships

Synthesis is an increasingly important component of scientific research, but training in synthetic research methods is not typically a part of graduate training. In addition to increasing graduate student participation in working groups, catalysis meetings and other activities, we propose to award graduate student fellowships for synthetic research. Each graduate fellow will be closely associated with a NESCent project (primarily a working group), and must be nominated and supervised by a member of that group. Each fellowship would be funded full-time for one semester, or at 50% funding for two semesters with 50% cost-sharing with their home institution. Fellows will be encouraged to be in residence at NESCent for at least part of their fellowship in order to benefit from and contribute to the in-house and visiting communities of NESCent scientists. We anticipate awarding 8 graduate fellowships per year. One important priority for this activity will be the recruitment of members from underrepresented groups, and applicants will be encouraged to recruit such candidates.

B. Developing & Disseminating New Tools for Evolutionary Informatics

The informatics program at NESCent has a twofold mission: to support the science activities funded through the open-proposal system and to promote synthetic evolutionary biology through a repertoire of carefully chosen cyberinfrastructure initiatives. Cyberinfrastructure is defined as the "coordinated aggregate of software, hardware and other technologies, as well as human expertise, required to support current and future discoveries" (Atkins, 2003). The emphasis at NESCent has been on cyberinfrastructure that helps drive data synthesis by building technologies that contribute to the availability, exchange and integration of evolutionary data. NESCent actively nurtures a community of

programming-savvy biologists and biology-savvy programmers that participate in the collaborative development of open-source informatics tools for evolutionary biology. NESCent also provides basic and advanced training in evolutionary informatics to future investigators. In years 6-10 we will continue the fundamental operations that underlie many of the major achievements of the Center. Our informatics program will strategically allocate its resources and **focus** its activities in response to careful consideration and advice from advisory boards and community members. We will continue our highly **synergistic** partnerships with sponsored science and with the broader community. Our **training and outreach** efforts will expand to include a broader range of topics and audiences.

1. Extending Current Programs

A core activity of NESCent's informatics group is to provide critical support for sponsored science. We do this by providing a suite of onsite and remote collaboration tools to all funded projects (e.g. working group wikis, mailing lists, video and audio conferencing, remote desktop and application sharing) and by developing custom software solutions for specific projects through dedicated programmer support. One example of a custom solution is a database produced for the "Primate Life Histories" working group. This resource integrates data from long-term field studies of wild populations of multiple primate species. It enables data entry, searching, browsing, and download over the web, enforces agreed-upon data coding standards, has scripts for bulk data upload from spreadsheets, and provides access security. This is a level of informatics support that would be out of reach of all but a few researchers at elite institutions.

Our dedicated support to sponsored science projects and Center administration will continue to evolve as technology improves and as we accumulate knowledge about how to effectively support remote collaborations. We will undertake periodic self-evaluations of the resources that are provided (such as wikis and teleconferencing technologies) and modify our support package accordingly. We will also add staff capacity to provide support for custom software solutions for the growing array of sponsored science activities at the Center. In particular we will add a senior staff position to oversee interactions with sponsored scientists during database design and user interface testing phases, to provide improved support for scientific/statistical programming projects, and to organize and direct training activities. This will allow us to offer better service to our sponsored activities and provides an individual who can work in a synergistic fashion with our science and EOG groups as we develop targeted and Center-wide activities.

NESCent's informatics program will continue to serve as a resource for the general evolutionary biology community. For instance the Community Summit identified an important role for NESCent serving as the gateway between individual scientists and powerful new cyberinfrastructure resources (such as the Open Science Grid). We will also continue to address critical community-wide needs for cyberinfrastructure that can only be effectively tackled by a national center. For example, the Generic Model Organism Database project ([GMOD](#)) provides community-wide user support for advanced open source software solutions in evolutionary genomics. The Dryad digital data repository initiative also provides a broad community service. NESCent is increasingly acting as a representative of the evolutionary biology community in a larger network of biodiversity, ecological, and environmental data centers that are collaborating on interoperability standards through a recently funded NSF- INTEROP grant (DBI-0753138) and a potential NSF DataNet project under review. Most of these initiatives have funding periods that extend well into years 6-10 and will continue to occupy the efforts of our staff.

We will continue to energetically promote collaborative, open source software development in evolutionary biology through the organization and sponsorship of hackathons (intense, week-long, collaborative programming sessions with specific software deliverables). Two hackathons have been held to date; they have been extremely successful in not only generating practical software tools but also greatly increasing productive interactions among the international evolutionary informatics community. A third hackathon on improving interoperability between evolutionary data repositories will be held in the first quarter of 2009. We will continue this successful program by sponsoring 4-6 hackathons during years 6-10. Examples of potential future topics include grid computing, semantic web applications, and visual workflow tools. We are also exploring the possibility of experimenting with "virtual hackathons" that allow a more diverse range of participants to collaborate within a virtual reality environment (e.g. [Croquet](#) or [Second Life](#)). This activity would dovetail well with our formative assessment of collaborative activities

(described below), allowing us to determine if it is possible to improve upon the community-building goals of the hackathon program by breaking down the physical walls of the Center.

Another key activity is our sponsorship of advanced training in synthetic science tools through summer courses and workshops. We will expand the training program with additional course offerings on new topics. The exact nature of the courses will be determined from a number of possibilities under consideration, including evolutionary biogeography, visualization, and the development and use of ontologies. A new course on statistical meta-analysis is already being planned for summer of 2009. We have a target of offering at least two courses each summer, and including among those at least two new topics within the next four years. These will be in addition to hosted courses offered through external funding (such as the annual Model Organism Database workshop that was launched in summer 2008).

We will also offer center-funded student internships in open source software (OSS) development as an extension to our popular Google Summer of Code™ program. These internships will supplement the relatively small number of projects available for funding through Google and external projects. In this program each student is paired with a mentor from the evoinformatics OSS development community, yet neither student nor mentor is expected to be in residence at NESCent, the same institution or even the same country; students and mentors will be invited to meet face-to-face at NESCent at the end of the summer. This nontraditional arrangement gives students invaluable training in the culture and practices of collaborative OSS development, which is generally accomplished by virtual communities.

2. New Informatics Initiatives

There are many areas where improvements to available cyberinfrastructure could have a major positive impact on synthetic evolutionary biology such as data availability, storage and processing capacity, software tools, and human resources. While NESCent fully intends to undertake major new cyberinfrastructure initiatives over the next five years, the exact nature of those initiatives will be determined by a strategic planning process in conjunction with input from the community. In some cases major initiatives must be opportunistic as we generally pursue such initiatives in partnership with other groups or as an outgrowth of particularly promising sponsored science. The priorities for major initiatives will be determined by NESCent Directors and our Advisory Board and evaluated according to an explicit set of criteria:

- The strength of commitment among the evolutionary biology community.
- The anticipated impact on facilitating evolutionary synthesis.
- The disciplinary diversity of the scientific communities that are affected.
- Feasibility and cost-effectiveness.
- The strength of the match to the informatics capabilities of the center.
- The extent to which the success of the initiative would depend on the participation of the Center.

A priority identified by the Community Summit is for NESCent to promote the usability and interoperability of major community databases in evolutionary biology. One such database is [TreeBASE](#), a primary repository of published phylogenetic data (Piel et al., 2002). It contains records from over 1600 publications and has an extensive user base. The NSF-funded Cyberinfrastructure for Phylogenetic Research (CIPRES) project (which expires in 2009) has developed a second-generation database (TreeBASE 2) scheduled for release in late 2008. TreeBASE 2, by the nature of the data it contains and the ways in which that data can be accessed, is anticipated to be an increasingly valuable resource for many different fields, including character evolution, biogeography, earth history, coevolution, phylogenetic method development, supertree construction, and conservation biology, to name a few. CIPRES and NESCent have reached an agreement whereby TreeBASE 2 would be moved from its current host (the San Diego Supercomputing Center) to NESCent prior to the expiration of the CIPRES project, and NESCent would make an initial commitment to host TreeBASE for up to five years. Since TreeBASE 2 has already been developed by CIPRES, only minor staff effort will be required for maintenance and upkeep. There is a demonstrated commitment to continued data curation by TreeBASE personnel, and a TreeBASE Foundation Board is being created to provide long-range planning for the database (see letter of collaboration from T Warnow and colleagues). Hosting TreeBASE will enable NESCent to better serve

the evolutionary biology community in several ways. First, through our Dryad program, NESCent is committed to integrating the data submission process of TreeBASE with that of Dryad, and hosting the database will considerably facilitate that task. Second, NESCent, by virtue of both its engaged resident scientific community and its active role in developing cyberinfrastructure for the evolutionary biology community, is in an excellent position to make sure that TreeBASE continues to be an effective tool for synthetic science. In particular, NESCent will work to ensure the compliance of TreeBASE with emerging interoperability services and standards during the term of the renewal. We believe hosting this resource will require only minor allocation of core resources but will provide an enormous service to the community.

We will initiate a new outreach and training activity in year 6. Activities such as the NESCent hackathons, NESCent's participation in the Google Summer of Code™, and the Phyloinformatics Summer Course, have demonstrated the value of strengthening collaborative ties within the large, but widely dispersed, evoinformatics community. Building such a community was recognized as one of NESCent's key achievements by attendees at the Community Summit. However the absence of any regular international conference at which such community ties can be strengthened has proven to be a major obstacle. The highly successful annual Bioinformatics Open Source Conference ([BOSC](#)), at which software developers discuss standards, share best practices, give hands-on tutorials in new software packages and emerging technologies, and report on efforts in progress, has proven to be useful to the related field of genome informatics. Based on this model, we will launch, in year 6, an annual meeting of OSS developers in evoinformatics to be held in conjunction with an evolutionary biology conference such as the joint SSE, SSB and ASN annual meeting. This conference is envisioned to include one or more keynote presentations, contributed presentations, and, most importantly, tutorials and working sessions at which participants can learn cutting-edge technologies and actively collaborate. This will initially be subsidized by modest NESCent core funding; after two years, we anticipate the meeting, if successful, to be supported largely by registration costs and to no longer require a subsidy. Dr. Rod Page has agreed to co-organize the first meeting (see letter of support).

C. Increasing the Public Understanding of Science – Education and Outreach

Through the coordinated efforts of center scientists and staff, NESCent works to improve evolutionary biology education, to disseminate up-to-date and emerging information on evolutionary research, and to expand opportunities in evolutionary biology for underrepresented groups. In the next five years, we will continue established partnerships with the biology education community, including on-going productive joint ventures with AIBS, Understanding Evolution, Evolutionary Studies Program EvoS, the National Academy of Sciences, the North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences, and the Encyclopedia of Life. Our efforts in years 6-10 will exhibit increased **focus** through the further development of the specific associations that have proven highly productive in the past four years. We will continue highly **synergistic** work within the Center through our use of the results of NESCent science and informatics activities as a base for our outreach efforts, and throughout the community with our various partners. Our best **training and outreach** activities will continue and expand.

1. Extending Current Programs

Our collaboration with the [Understanding Evolution](#) (UE) project at the University of California at Berkeley' Museum of Paleontology continues to gain momentum as we share data and resources in the development, dissemination, and assessment of educational materials. Our [Education in the News podcasting](#) NSF CCLI phase 1 project was just funded in collaboration with the UE group (DUE-0837015). This project combines NESCent's access to cutting edge science with UE's expertise in public dissemination of educational products. With Judy Scotchmoor of the UE program, we are developing a CCLI phase 2 program that will establish an "Evolution Undergraduate Lounge" section within the UE website. This section will focus on providing appropriate educational materials for undergraduate students and will have a strong Web2.0 component to engage the student audience and promote community building.

NESCent will further develop our sponsorship of and collaboration with groups that focus on evolutionary education. For example, as part of the Evolution Across the Curriculum (EvAC) group (led by Gordon

Uno) we are developing examples of how evolution can illuminate, and be illuminated by key biological concepts and processes such as photosynthesis, cell cycle, genes and genomes, immune response and conservation. We will use these examples to move the EvAC concept into implementation and formal assessment phases through teacher workshops, seminars, and classroom interactions.

Similarly, NESCent is a participant in the [EvoS](#) project, an NSF funded program centered at Binghamton University and led by David Sloan Wilson. The program uses evolutionary theory as a unifying theme across all fields of study, including the humanities and arts, and is open to all students, not just biology majors. NESCent is represented on the EvoS advisory board, and we support the EvoS wiki site. We will work with EvoS to develop further collaborations as the project grows. In particular, we are developing collaborative linkages between the EvoS project and Understanding Evolution to develop online resources for undergraduate students and instructors.

NESCent's Education and Outreach staff will continue to serve many key functions in the operation of the Center's in-house programs. These include the organization of the seminar and postdoc professional development series, contributing educational and other content to the NESCent website, producing a quarterly newsletter to keep the evolutionary biology community informed of the activities at the Center, serving as a communications office, producing promotional material for the Center, promoting the Center through exhibition booths at major scientific conferences, and coordinating telecasts and videocasts of scientific meetings and presentations. In addition, the Education and Outreach staff members work with all groups and scientists visiting the Center to discuss the development of broader impact activities and help assess the best ways that their science may be translated to the public and educational community. For example our staff worked with one working group that chose to use their supplementary funds to present a workshop on biogeography at NABT.

2. New Education and Outreach Initiatives

New EOG initiatives will continue to arise opportunistically out of our interactions with scientists, teachers, professional societies, and partner institutions. Years 6-10 will include an intensified and broadened focus on assessment of all of our education and outreach programs, as discussed in the next section of the proposal. We will target three major new efforts in years 6-10.

We will actively solicit and review proposals with a focus on science education and outreach through our normal proposal process, increasing our support for community driven education and outreach activities. Such projects might include science pedagogy, citizen science or the effective communication of scientific activities. In addition, we will also initiate targeted activities in areas of particular promise. For example, we are planning a targeted working group that will bring together individuals that are engaging the public through the concept of 'citizen science'. This group will work towards developing methods and resources aimed at expanding the public understanding of science, and specifically promoting public interaction with evolutionary scientists and research projects. This working group will expand current collaborations with the NC Museum of Natural Sciences in Raleigh, the education team of the Encyclopedia of Life (Harvard), and the Coalition for the Public Understanding of Science (COPUS) Year of Science 2009.

We will expand our training initiatives by developing a new summer short course for high school teachers designed to update their conceptual base by focusing on new findings and expanding areas of modern evolutionary biology. This course will bring teachers to the Center for an intensive week of lectures, hands-on demonstrations, and interactive groups and will be designed to provide certification credit for teacher continuing education. Center staff, scientists, guest lecturers and postdocs will serve as instructors in the course. We will particularly target teachers from schools with high minority populations.

As a part of our commitment to broadening the demographics of evolutionary biology, we will initiate a new activity entitled 'Diversifying Evolution'. This activity will support a working group that involves coordination of existing programs that promote evolutionary biology research and teaching experiences at Historically Minority Universities and to diverse underrepresented groups at universities, colleges, and K-12 institutions. Leadership for this group comes from Scott Edwards (Harvard) and Joseph Graves (NC A&T University) both of whom are members of NESCent's Senior Advisory Board and from the NESCent Directors and staff. This group will work to expand our connections with minority institutions and

students, recruit individuals from these institutions to our science and informatics programs, build a resource for disseminating research and teaching opportunities, and provide linkages to promote existing programs.

D. Center Wide Activities

Although for convenience we often discuss NESCent's branches as individual activities, in practice, most of our most important activities are a result of interaction among them. We hope that through our examples, such synergies have been communicated. Many of the activities discussed above are in reality not the province of one branch, but represent a significant Center wide commitment. Examples of such activities include expanded educational activities, our efforts to increase representation of underrepresented groups in evolutionary biology, and some of our targeted science programs.

As mentioned above there was substantial interest in a targeted initiative in visualization tools at our September 2008 Community Summit. We anticipate that this activity in particular will be Center-wide in scope, capitalizing on synergies among the sponsored science, informatics, and education and outreach programs. For example, a planned initiative in the visualization of evolutionary data might begin out of a one-time meeting involving biologists at the Center, visualization experts from computer science and other fields, educators, cognitive scientists and science journalists. It could be followed-up with a suite of interlocked activities. A sabbatical residency by a visualization expert could initiate one or more collaborative projects with other resident scientists and existing working groups. Visualization software, images or web applications that make complex evolutionary data visually accessible in novel ways could be designed and executed by graphics professionals in collaboration with the informatics staff. These products could be disseminated to classrooms through our teacher training workshops, and to the public through our existing outreach partnerships. Thus, targeted initiatives can take full advantage of NESCent's resources to simultaneously help drive synthetic science, lead to new informatics resources, and promote the public understanding of evolutionary biology.

E. Summary

NESCent's activities over years 6-10 will build on our most successful attributes: community driven activities, highly synergistic projects and the leveraging our impact by broad collaborations with groups engaged in science, policy, informatics, outreach and education. The set of activities we propose grows directly out of many of the most exciting initiatives suggested at the Community Summit, and will allow us to further lead by recruiting the most promising activities to the Center and developing programs of broad impact on biology as well as the wider world.

IV PUTTING PROGRAMS INTO EFFECT

A. Developing Collaborative Research Assessment Plans

As the Center has matured, we have developed a more focused and formal approach to assess Center activities. By the end of year 5 we will have established three different tiers of assessment that will be fully operational during years 6-10 of the Center's existence.

The first tier of assessment is to systematically track aspects of participants and activities at the Center and compare these measures with specific strategic targets. For example, we track applications received and funded, disciplinary fields and demographics of applicants and participants, meetings held, etc., in order to understand how our day-to-day activities are meeting these goals. This level of assessment is facilitated by an internal database that has recently come online designed specifically for this purpose. Disciplinary and demographic data are now being collected as part of the application and reimbursement process for all Center participants. In developing a protocol for this assessment, we have laid out objectives and measures; our success at meeting these objectives will regularly be evaluated. A few examples of such programmatic goals are: to receive and fund applications from the full range of disciplines and sub-disciplines in biology; to ensure that our funded scientists are geographically, ethnically and racially diverse; and that the number of females is at minimum representative of potential

applicant pools. A full detailed plan of objectives and assessments may be found on our [public document](#) page.

In order to assess our service to the evolutionary biology community, we will conduct regular community-wide surveys. The Center has already conducted such surveys as part of the planning process for several informatics initiatives (including Dryad and GMOD). We will expand our survey program to provide specific assessment of how well NESCent is serving the community.

Specific assessment plans are to be used for individual initiatives, in particular for courses and other educational and outreach activities. For example, our new CCLI grant focuses on assessment of the Evolution in the News program in collaboration with the School of Education at the University of North Carolina. Customized assessment mechanisms are also in place for activities such as the NABT symposium, the Phyloinformatics and GMOD summer courses, and the Summer of Code internships.

The second tier of assessment is analysis of products resulting from NESCent funding in order to understand the broader impact of NESCent sponsored activities. In addition to simply collecting data on numbers of publications, grant proposals or new software, we have begun to assess patterns of impact of such products. One example of such an analysis of NESCent publications was undertaken by Sarah Carrier, a graduate student in Information and Library Sciences at UNC. This survey of NESCent publications from years 1-3 compares attributes of each NESCent publication with those of three non-NESCent publications randomly chosen from the same issue of the same journal. Each NESCent and non-NESCent paper was compared in terms of citation impact factor, number of authors, and number of institutions. A preliminary analysis suggests that there are consistent mean differences between NESCent and non-NESCent publications in terms of collaboration patterns and impact. Small sample size and heterogeneity of the data preclude formal statistical analyses at this stage, but this initial survey suggests that, on average, NESCent publications have higher citation impact and involve greater collaboration among authors, disciplines and institutions than comparable, non-NESCent publications.

Citations and collaboration for NESCent and non-NESCent publications, through February 2008.		
Metric:	NESCent publication	non-NESCent publication
Citation impact factor	5.44	3.83
# of authors	4.99	4.15
# of disciplines	3.19	2.46
# of institutions	3.34	2.34

Carrier's survey also revealed that publications involving NESCent research were underreported to NESCent by more than 25%; underreporting of collaborations resulting from NESCent activities is probably even greater. These findings have motivated improvements currently being made to our reporting process. In years 6-10, we will expand such assessments in collaboration with Jane Greenberg and students from the UNC School of Information and Library Sciences.

A third tier of assessment is formative analysis, the results of which can be used to improve the ways that the center promotes synthetic evolutionary biology. The focus will be on the behaviors and attitudes of scientists towards collaboration, and how such behavior is changed as a result of NESCent funding. In order to conduct such assessments, we will collaborate with Professor Jonathon Cummings (Associate Professor of Management) and Luck Dookchitra (PhD Student in Management) from the Fuqua School of Business at Duke University. This project will begin in January 2009 (year 5 of the current grant). Professor Cummings has conducted several evaluations of NSF programs, including projects in Knowledge and Distributed Intelligence (KDI; Cummings & Kiesler, 2005) and Information Technology Research (ITR; Cummings & Kiesler, 2007). His current work focuses on Virtual Organizations, and specifically how to increase the likelihood of success for research collaborators working together across institutions (Cummings et al, 2008; Whitfield, 2008). He has also developed software to facilitate the collection, analysis, and visualization of evaluation data (<http://www.projectassessment.org/nescent> --

username: demo; password: demo). Within NESCent, Professor Cummings will focus on four programs through which participants produce knowledge and build relationships at NESCent and beyond: (1) working groups, (2) catalysis meetings, (3) post-doc and sabbatical visits, and (4) informatics hackathons. His formative evaluation (Scriven, 1967) will include observations, interviews, and surveys to provide feedback on the effectiveness of these programs within NESCent. A key advantage of formative evaluation is that experimental methods can be used to assess the impact that interventions have on the programs. For example we may try different follow ups to group support such as follow-up face-to-face meetings, versus follow-up virtual meetings; we may compare productivity and community-building in physical versus “virtual” hackathons.

For each of the four programs, the formative evaluation will examine factors that contribute to successful outcomes. In the case of working groups, factors such as communication within and across institutions will be linked to outcomes such as knowledge production (publications and conference presentations). In the case of catalysis meetings, factors such as disciplinary affiliation will be linked to outcomes such as perspective taking (shift in views within the discussed domains and subsequent pursuit of new questions within and among related domains). In the case of postdoc and sabbatical visits, factors such as length of time spent onsite and NESCent participation (research collaboration and working group participation) will be linked to productivity and impact. In the case of informatics hackathons, factors such as prior relationships among participants will be linked to outcomes such as adoption of shared standards and code. Because these programs continue on a cyclical basis throughout the year, they can be assessed before, during, and after completion. For example, in the case of catalysis meetings, assessments can be made to see which participants knew each other in advance of the meetings, who interacted heavily during the meetings, and who formed sustainable collaborations after the meetings. Moreover, as mentioned above, experimental methods can be used to assess changes in activities, such as a random sample of participants who take part in informatics hackathons virtually rather than at NESCent. Importantly, formative evaluations can provide critical feedback on the Centers programs in a timely manner.

This analysis will provide NESCent with important information about the value of its programs in building communities and in creating a culture of collaboration. Collaborating with an active social scientist will be particularly valuable, as NESCent will serve as a case study that contributes to a larger literature on the nature of scientific collaborations.

B. Leadership and Management

NESCent's leadership is a shared responsibility reflecting the fact that the Center is a collaborative effort of three universities. Currently NESCent has an overall Director from Duke University (Smith at 50% effort) and Associate Directors from UNC (Kingsolver and Vision at 25% and 50% effort, respectively) and NCSU (Wiegmann at 25% effort). These Associate Directors serve as both the PI's for the subcontracts to the contributing universities, as well as directors for each of the “branches” of NESCent: Science and Synthesis (Kingsolver), Informatics (Vision) and Education and Outreach (Wiegmann). The performance of the Directors is assessed annually by the Senior Advisory Board. Those assessments are forwarded to the appropriate university administrator, and the respective administrators of the three institutions are responsible for ensuring the effectiveness of the Center's leadership structure.

As we look forward into years 6-10 we will maintain this basic structure, with a few specific changes. We will ensure that collaborating institutions maintain a high degree of participation, and also that appropriate scientific leadership is in place as the focus and expertise of the Center evolves.

Smith and Kingsolver will be stepping down as Director and Associate Director of Science after year 5. Duke University is currently searching for a full time Director, who is expected to be in place by the beginning of year 6 of the Center. This individual will assume overall leadership of the Center as well as initially the Science programs and be responsible for an expanded program of Center outreach, both to the evolutionary biology community and fields beyond. In addition, a full time Assistant Director of Science (Ph.D. level, but non-faculty position) will be appointed by the winter or spring of 2009 (year 5 of the current grant). The Assistant Director of Science will assume some of the routine management tasks of Kingsolver (management of the grant review process), and be responsible for coordinating reporting

activities, supervise the administration of the internal database, and also oversee the survey and assessment activities of the Center. At this time Vision and Wiegmann intend to continue their roles into the first few years of renewal period. Whether Kingsolver will be formally replaced by an additional Associate Director will be decided once the new Director is in place.

In the long term, we will ensure that at least one Director or Associate Director is appointed from each institution, in order to maintain the Center as a fully collaborative organization. We do not believe it is necessary to have a single individual Associate Director for each branch. For example, it may be reasonable to consider more than one Associate Director assuming significant responsibilities for Informatics and the Center Director assuming major responsibility for Science, Education and Outreach or Informatics activities. The most important factor is to ensure that as NESCent activities continue to remain an integrated whole, that there is appropriate and broad expertise among the senior leadership team, and that this team continues to function in a highly collaborative manner.

In addition to the senior leadership of the Center, major decisions will continue to be made in consultation with an [Operations Committee](#) (OC). This committee consists of the Directors, as well as one individual from each of the collaborating institutions and one postdoctoral fellow. This structure ensures broad input into the functioning of the Center.

C. Ensuring Continual Community Input

Ensuring continual community input is critical and we propose several extensions and modifications of the current practices.

The first modification we propose is a reorganization of our advisory boards. We currently have two boards. A [Senior Advisory Board](#) meets annually and advises Center Directors on Center performance and strategic planning for future activities. A [Science Advisory Board](#) is responsible for the review of proposals and advising the Center leadership on Science programs. This group meets once or twice a year (occasionally the second round of proposals is reviewed remotely). With the endorsement of the Senior Advisory Board we propose merging these boards into a single Advisory Board. The most significant benefit of this model will be that the same group that provides the basic advice to the Center on program funding and knows the most about our science programs, will be called upon to provide broader advice on overall Center direction. Under the prior model, the Senior Advisory Board had little direct knowledge of the patterns of applications, the priorities made during funding decisions, or the specific projects funded. We believe this change will make the overall advice process more efficient and more effective. We will ensure that the population of the advisory board is sufficiently broad to provide advice on Informatics initiatives as well as Education and Outreach programs. We will also continue to ensure broad diversity with regard to field, gender and demographic characteristics.

We propose to use community summits as a way to gather advice from our stakeholders. We will plan to schedule additional community summits during the next 5 years. One such summit will be devoted to Center-wide strategic planning in year 7. The remaining summits will likely be targeted towards specific Science, Informatics or Education initiatives.

Leaders and representatives from the major NSF synthesis centers (NCEAS, iPlant and NIMBioS) participated in the September 2008 community summit at NESCent in order to discuss issues of common concern and potential new programs and synergies. With these Centers, we will schedule an annual leadership meeting to ensure maximal scientific and administrative interchange.

Finally, we will extend our outreach efforts from evolutionary biologists to the broader scientific community. Such outreach will include attendance at meetings such as the microbiology, neuroscience and/or cell biology meetings, as well key social science meetings. Additionally, the Directors will undertake more an aggressive campaign of individually encouraging potential applicants in areas that are under-represented at the Center and/or of emerging interest to evolutionary biology. Finally, as mentioned above, we will initiate a program to regularly survey the evolutionary biology community (through evoldir and other mailing lists) in order to assess community perceptions about funding

opportunities, successful programs, and gaps in our activities. The survey process should help raise the profile of the Center.

D. Institutional Support

In recognition of the unique distinction of hosting NESCent in the Research Triangle, the three collaborating Universities have made important institutional commitments toward the success of the Center. These commitments include:

- Each institution will ensure that the institution is represented by a Director or Associate Director, and each institution will share in support by way of compensation or release time to make the participation of that individual (or individuals) possible.
- Financial support (current levels; we expect this support to continue in years 6-10):
 - Duke University provides support for a Director, including salary, and other necessary support. In addition, Duke provides 25% of rent costs and a discretionary budget to support Center activities in the amount of \$120,000 per year. This discretionary money has been used to fund activities that build community within our in house group; local outreach activities such as our Darwin Day events; partial salary support for staff members; receptions and other events to bring visiting scientists together with in house scientists; Triangle working group activities; books for our library; further furniture purchase, and a host of minor other items.
 - UNC provides support for the Associate Director of Informatics (Vision) in the form of \$50,000 annually for a lab manager.
 - NCSU provides institutional support in the form of funds for the Associate Director of Education and Outreach (Wiegmann) in support of his research program (equivalent to \$36,000 per year).
- Each University will ensure that faculty are given release time to participate in Center activities as Triangle Scholars.
- The three universities have signed a Memorandum of Agreement that details these commitments and further contains provisions that offer flexibility in spending the funds available to the Center from the three institutions.

In addition NESCent receives an enormous intangible benefit from its proximity to the three collaborating universities. Faculty, postdocs and students from the Universities participate in many NESCent activities, and are often invited to participate in working groups and catalysis meetings by the PIs of those events. NESCent postdocs and sabbatical scholars often attend scientific events at the universities, and faculty from the universities serve as postdoc scientific collaborators and mentors. Funds from the Duke University Provost supports Triangle working groups (groups that undergo peer review, but are funded from non-core sources as they are largely composed of scientists from the local area), and each university allows for release time for Triangle sabbatical scholars, local faculty that are in residence at NESCent for a semester. The library resources from all Universities are available to all scholars and Duke University provides significant computational infrastructure support.

E. Strategic Planning for the Future

As part of a renewed emphasis on planning and assessment, NESCent will undertake a series of strategic planning initiatives in preparation for a year 7 site visit. These initiatives will include a comprehensive self study, and the generation of a strategic plan. This plan will include an analysis of NESCent's programs and the community's needs and a critical look at our current programs, with a focus on the results of the above assessment activities. We will use this plan to guide our selection of targeted calls for proposals in year 8 and potential new cyberinfrastructure initiatives. In addition to strategic planning for years 8-10 of Center funding, we will also look towards ways that NESCent can develop greater self sufficiency in view maintaining the Center beyond year 10. After developing this study we will engage in considerable community discussion, with surveys, a major community summit, and extensive discussions with our Advisory Board.

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- (references with "view copy" may be found on our [public documents page](#))**